

Jnanadeepa

Pune Journal of Religious Studies

ISSN 2249-1503

www.punejournal.in

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4284702

Stable URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4284702>

Sin as The Mirror Image of the Person: Initiating
A Functional Approach to the Doctrine of Sin
Mathew Jayanth, SJ

Abstract: That the sense of sin has eroded, partially at least, from the Christian consciousness is an incontestable fact. Some even hail this as the emancipation of the Christian psyche from the shackles of tradition and the opening of newer vistas for the progress of humanity. No wonder, then, that even preachers and theologians shy away from discussing sin. The fear is that, since sin is supposedly the forte of the old-fashioned, preaching or writing about sin would automatically place one with the obscurantist. People would rather keep quiet than speak about sin and forfeit their place among the progressives.

Keywords: Erosion of sense of sin, Guilt, Mirror image of person, Doctrine of sin

Cite as: Jayanth, Mathew. (2008). Sin As The Mirror Image Of the Person: Initiating A Functional Approach to the Doctrine of Sin (Version 1.0). *Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies*, Jan-June 2008 (Vol 11/2), 76-96. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4284702>

20001-07-05 | Updated on Nov 20, 2020

Sin As The Mirror Image Of The Person: Initiating A Functional Approach To The Doctrinre of Sin

Mathew Jayanth, SJ

Department of Systematic Theology,
Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune 14

Introduction: Stating The Problematic

That the sense of sin has eroded, partially at least, from the Christian consciousness is an incontestable fact. Some even hail this as the emancipation of the Christian psyche from the shackles of tradition and the opening of newer vistas for the progress of humanity. No wonder, then, that even preachers and theologians shy away from discussing sin. The fear is that, since sin is supposedly the forte of the old-fashioned, preaching or writing about sin would automatically place one with the obscurantist. People would rather keep quiet than speak about sin and forfeit their place among the progressives.

Perhaps this state of affairs should not be very surprising given the way the doctrine of sin has been handled in the past. Historically, the theological treatment of sin, especially from the Middle Ages on, began to assume legalistic and moralistic overtones with the emphasis on the matter of sin, the seriousness of sin, the classification of sin, the culpability for sin and so on. In the process of trying to achieve a certain objectivity regarding sin, the doctrine of sin lost its essential link with the other doctrines of faith. This isolation of the doctrine of sin obscured its full import for Christian living and gradually, and not without the influence of the Augustinian rigorism, paved the way for the development of an unhealthy sense of fear, guilt and shame. Sin came to be primarily associated with the infringement of certain norms and prescriptions, especially in the area of sex, requiring the sacrament of reconciliation. Thus, not infrequently do we come across people

approaching the sacrament of reconciliation with the magical notion that a mere enumeration of sins to the confessor effects a general cleansing and brings about a sense of relief from the burden of fear, guilt and shame. As a consequence of such developments, the doctrine of sin itself came to be looked upon with suspicion.

What is at stake here is not merely the doctrine of sin, but the very integrity of the Christian faith. For the doctrine of sin makes a crucial contribution to the comprehensive understanding of the Christian faith. First of all, Christianity is a soteriological religion, a religion that focuses on the salvation of human persons and their world. The whole divine economy – from Creation to Incarnation and the final recapitulation of all in Christ – is centred on the notion of salvation. In the absence of a genuine doctrine of sin, the concept of salvation remains vague and the idea of the divine economy of salvation fails to convey its depth of meaning. Second, the Christian doctrines concerning the church, sacraments, mission and practically all other doctrines of faith are linked to the offer of God's salvation in Jesus Christ. The doctrine of sin clarifies the nature of this salvation and, thereby, helps us to grasp the significance of the doctrines of the church in their entirety insofar as they are related to God's salvation. This being the case, a lack of an authentic doctrine of sin obscures the main tenets of the Christian faith. .

This calls for a re-positioning of the doctrine of sin that would facilitate the overcoming of its prolonged isolation from the other doctrines of faith and its integration into the larger soteriological framework, which, in fact, is the general horizon for understanding the various aspects of the Christian faith. The modern disillusionment with sin and its gradual disappearance from the Christian consciousness is not unconnected with the displacement of the doctrine of sin from its soteriological context. Moreover, the loss incurred by other doctrines of faith in terms of meaning and coherence is also linked to the isolation of the doctrine of sin. These, once again, go to prove the necessity of relocating the doctrine of sin squarely within the totality of faith and reclaiming it for the Christian faith.

Methodological Presuppositions

The re-positioning of the doctrine of sin necessarily calls for an effective methodology. The two commonly used methods at present are the method of biblical theology and the interdisciplinary method. The former focuses on the analysis of the biblical narratives of sin as well as on the analysis of the various Hebrew and Greek words for sin in the bible.¹ On the basis of these, theology seeks to understand the root cause of sin, its universality, the nature and meaning of sin and its consequences at the personal and societal levels. Usually the method begins with the narratives of the Creation and the Fall and quickly moves on to the narrative of the redemption accomplished by Jesus Christ. Such a method is ahistorical insofar as it neglects to take into account the contours of sin in its historical developments and manifestations. Secondly, this method tries to treat sin objectively insofar as it seeks to understand the origin and spread of sin, the nature of sin and its consequences. This method is valuable as it establishes the biblical basis of the doctrine of sin and also provides an objective understanding of the reality of sin and its various dimensions. However, the method is inadequate because in its attempt to generate objective data, it tends to overlook the function of sin in the bible.²

The interdisciplinary method aims at bringing the insights from the human and social sciences to the understanding of the reality of sin. This method, therefore, builds on and amplifies the discoveries made by the biblical method with the help of other disciplines. Accordingly, psychology greatly contributes to a deeper perception of sin by showing the psychic structure of human persons and the roots of loneliness and insecurity, guilt and shame, inauthenticity and alienation from self, and a myriad other psychological experiences such as inner conflicts and the operation of the subconscious factors affecting human behaviour³. Similarly, the insights from social sciences regarding socio-economic alienation, the functions of purity and pollution, violence, social oppression and discrimination, and exploitation of the weak and the powerless help broaden the understanding of sin by the inclusion of social structural sin.⁴ Again, the philosophical enquiries into human existence reveal the problems of inauthentic existence, the experience of meaninglessness, purposelessness and, thereby, highlight the human predicament, which necessarily enhances our notion of sin.⁵

Furthermore, the discoveries in the field of neuroscience and the study of genetics have shed light on the element of determinism or conditioning built into the brain structure and the structure of the genes. These discoveries offer necessary corrections to the traditional simplistic understanding of sin.⁶ Thus, the interdisciplinary method makes available wider categories for understanding the doctrine of sin. However, it is beyond the scope of this method to provide a theology of sin. Therefore, the interdisciplinary method is also inadequate for a theological approach to the doctrine of sin.

While the biblical method highlights the reality of sin and the interdisciplinary method underscores the contemporary significance of sin in the experience of the modern humans, they are insufficient for a theological re-positioning of sin within the comprehensive framework of the Christian faith. The question that confronts us is: What kind of an approach to sin will enable us to re-position sin in a manner that will facilitate the recovery of an authentic understanding of sin? Theologically the question boils down to the issue of theological method and can be reformulated: What theological method will enable us to move from the knowledge of sin to the function of sin?

This shift from the reality of sin to the function of sin is a shift in favour of a functional understanding of sin. Here it is essential to emphasize that the functional approach should not be understood in performative terms, where the focus will be on what sin does to the sinner as well as to those sinned against. If the focus remains the same, then the stress will fall primarily on the reality and the consequences of sin, and, there would be hardly any change in the method of approach to sin.

Rather, the functional approach is to be understood in terms of method. It presupposes the knowledge of the reality of sin and its consequences. But moving beyond, this approach asks: What function does the doctrine of sin perform in terms of its revealing power? The theological import of this question can be explained thus: As we all agree, the concept of sin, in one way or another, is present in all religions. If its function were to create, as already mentioned, a sense of fear, guilt, shame and other such negative emotions and feelings, then the persistence of the notion of sin becomes inexplicable. In this

context, it is probably right to say that religions with their idea of sin do not create the negative feelings and emotions. Rather, it is the experience of negativities and one's positive contribution to them that generate the feeling of fear, guilt and shame. The doctrine of sin confirms this. Thus, the methodological significance of the functional approach is to be viewed from the perspective of what the religions want their doctrine of sin to do.

Coming specifically to the Christian religion, we may ask: What does the Christian faith want its doctrine of sin to accomplish? In other words, what specific function does the doctrine of sin fulfil in the Christian religion?⁷ It is this crucial question that will engage us in this essay. It must be admitted at the outset that identifying the function of the doctrine of sin within Christianity is a formidable task. For it presupposes a comprehensive grasp of the Christian worldview or the horizon of understanding within which the notion of sin operates. On the other hand, one's own horizon of understanding eludes easy conceptualisation precisely because, first, it functions as an unthematized background of all cognitive processes, and, second, the horizon keeps on changing. In any case, it is important to delineate, briefly at least, the main tenets of the Christian horizon of understanding in order to understand the function of the doctrine of sin in Christian religion.

The primary factor in the Christian horizon of understanding that is crucial for the functional approach to sin is the view of the human person. In other words, the function of sin in Christianity is predicated upon the notion of the human person. Linking the doctrine of sin with the doctrine of the human person can shed light on the function that sin fulfils in Christianity. Accordingly, in this paper I will argue that the function of sin is to reveal the human person to himself/herself by offering a mirror image of the person. Sin offers a mirror image because it reflects the existential status of a person called to live an authentic life. It reveals the disfigurement and disintegration of the person that result from sin with a view to advancing the authentic humanity of a person. Hence, the doctrine of sin has relevance insofar as it provides a contrasting image of the person and, thereby, reinforces the image of an authentic person.

From this perspective, the functional approach to sin emphasizes the revelatory power of sin in relation to the fundamental vocation of human persons to become fully and authentically human. The biblical testimony that the human person bears the image of God (Gen. 1:27) points to the call to become a full human person. The image of sin, on the other hand, offers a contrast: it offers the opposite of the image of God; the opposite of the basic vocation to be authentically human. At this juncture, it is important to underscore the point that the contrasting image provided by sin is not an artificial construction. If it were so, then the doctrine of sin would have only a heuristic function. That is to say, it would amount to an artificial construal of sin in order to generate a counter image of the person. It would imply the denial of the experiential dimension of sin.

Rather than an artificial construal, sin is a human reality located in the experiential realm of human becoming. It refers to the experience of being distanced from the goal of becoming an authentic human person. As such, humans experience it as a dynamic process intertwined with the project of actualising the fundamental vocation to become human. It is precisely the complexity and ambiguity resulting from the intimate link between the two processes in the sphere of human experience that necessitate the assistance of the mirror image to explicate the real trajectory of the process of becoming authentically human.

We have, up to this point, introduced the problematic we are addressing, and specified the methodological presuppositions for a functional approach to the doctrine of sin. We have also stated the central argument of the paper and offered some necessary clarifications. We shall now proceed to substantiate the argument that sin offers a mirror image of the person. For this, we shall first analyse the Christian theological understanding of the human person for the purpose of identifying some of the constitutive elements that make up a holistic vision of being human. In this connection we shall briefly analyse such themes as the human being as a creature, the human being as standing in a special relationship with God, the human being as essentially social and sexual, the human being as embodied and as related to and engaged with the world through action, the human being as dynamic and free

and, finally, the human being as called to a final destiny. These elements become the point of reference for understanding the reality of sin. Using these reference points we shall analyse, in the second place, the revelatory function of the doctrine of sin. Here we shall underscore the fact that sin as a mirror image reveals the opposite of becoming authentically human. This revelation makes us aware of the challenges involved in conforming ourselves to the Christian vision of the human person.

Anthropological Foundations

We have already pointed out that a comprehensive analysis of the Christian horizon of understanding is necessary for approaching sin from a functional perspective. Since such a task is impossible to undertake in the limited space of an article, we shall limit ourselves to the vision of the human person enshrined in the Christian horizon of understanding. The intention here is to outline the image of the person that emerges from within the Christian worldview along with its main characteristics. This image, as we shall subsequently see, will help us to examine the contrasting or mirror image portrayed by sin and to determine the function of the doctrine of sin in the Christian horizon of understanding.⁸

Rather than furnishing a scientific explanation of the human phenomenon, the Christian theological anthropology is primarily concerned about providing the meaning, value and purpose of human existence in its totality. The whole divine economy – Creation, Incarnation and Redemption – presents itself as an explication of the God-intended meaning, value and purpose of human beings and their world.⁹ It is this overarching horizon of understanding that defines the human person from the Christian faith perspective. When the Christian faith affirms the reality of the human person, it is always an affirmation of the human person as one who stands before God – God who, as the origin and destiny of human persons, reveals the God-self in Jesus Christ as the source of the meaning, value and purpose of humans and their world. However, the Christian faith does not envisage the human person standing before God in isolation; rather he/she stands before God as a member of the human community and as one who is historically situated in the world. In other words, essential to standing before God

is standing **with** others in solidarity and standing **in** the world as an integral part of the cosmic process with the expectation and hope of realizing the God-given purpose. This, in a nutshell, is the core of the Christian vision of the human person. We need to unfold this vision drawing insights from the scriptures.

Human Being as Creature:

Central to the biblical affirmation about the human person is that one is essentially a creature. This is not an objective scientific statement about the origin of the human person. But rather one locates here the theological or faith affirmation regarding the specific nature of the relationship between human beings and God. It can be described as a relationship of dependence, provided that the concept 'dependence' is understood not in terms of enslavement, but in terms of the on-going creative activity of God that constantly sustains us in existence. It is this relationship that is emphasized when the Christian theological anthropology portrays the person as standing before God.

Human Being as Loved into Existence:

The characteristic of this divine (Creator) – human (creature) relationship is expressed in theology by the notion of grace. Grace, as the *dharma* of God,¹⁰ as the loving disposition of the Creator toward the creature, signifies the entirely gratuitous ways of God's self-giving manifested in the act of creation, in holding the entire creation together in existence as well as in sustaining everything. The notion of grace furnishes the *raison d'être* for human existence: human beings are loved into existence and the same divine love keeps us in existence while leading us to our fulfilment in God.¹¹ In a way, the concept of grace recapitulates the whole divine economy in relation to human beings and their world. Once again, the proper human response to the grace of God is to 'stand before God'. As we shall presently explain, this graced relationship provides the foundation for other human relationships.

Human Being as Called to Communion:

From this portrayal of human persons in relation to God, we shall now move on to the human relationship with other human beings. The Christian anthropology is emphatic with regard to the social nature of

human persons. When the scripture depicts the creation of human persons, it pays special attention to the fact that humanity is created male and female (Gen 1:27). The implication is that authentic humanity does not reside in the male or in the female; it is to be realized through a process of communion among persons. The same point is emphasized in the *Pastoral Constitution of the Church in the Modern World*, where it says that God did not create human beings as solitary beings¹². That is to say, communion among persons is a necessary condition for the realization of one's personhood. Thus, from the perspective of human-human relationship we get a picture of the person as one who is always related and moving out of oneself to other human persons.

Human Being as Oriented Toward Others:

This ecstatic nature of human persons is emphasized in human sexuality. It symbolizes the human need for the other to attain one's own humanity. Human sexuality connotes the essential other-orientedness of human beings. That is to say, human beings attain their authentic nature as human persons only by going out of themselves to others in love, intimacy and communion. Sexuality represents the energy that enables us to break open the enclosure created by our self-centredness and to move out toward life-enhancing relationships with other human persons. Sexuality reveals to us that one can become an authentic human person only by relating to others and not in isolation from others.

Human Being as Rooted in The World:

A third level of human relationality manifests itself in the sphere of human-world relationship. Like the divine-human, and human-human relationships, the relationship between humans and the world is constitutive of being human. The scripture is not shy to speak of human dependence on the created universe. According to the book of Genesis, human beings are related to the earth from the moment of their origins and continue to depend on the world for their sustenance (Gen. 2:7ff). Solidarity with and dependence on the world are integral to being human. For, human existence would be unthinkable without an environment. The essential link with the environment entails human responsibility for the created world. Becoming an authentic human person

presupposes not only the acknowledgement of one's dependence on the environment but also the active dimension of caring for and promoting the well-being of God's creation. This way of relating to the world is also a concrete expression of one's relationship with God and with other human persons. Thus, the emerging picture shows human beings as deeply rooted in the world.

Human Beings as Body-Persons:

These three dimensions of relationship are predicated upon the embodied existence of human persons. It is embodiment that gives solidity to the picture of the human person. That is to say, it is as body-persons that we stand before God in a love relationship, we enter into life - enhancing communion with other human persons, and we relate to the world around us. Body enables us to actualise our multiple relationships because it fulfils the conditions for relationships. First, embodiment allows us to locate ourselves within the vast universe and, second, it gives us a specific identity as human persons. Our location and our identity facilitate our reaching out toward others and to the world. In relation to other human persons, body enables us to actualise our ecstatic nature as symbolized by sexuality by becoming a body-gift to others. It is in our body that we become a self-gift to others.¹³ In this way, embodiment becomes a precondition to becoming an authentic human person in relation to other human persons.

Human Beings as Engaged in Action:

As already mentioned, the relationship with and openness to the world is an essential requirement for the realization of one's humanity. This openness to the world is made possible by our existence as body-persons. Human activity in the world is an eminent expression of this openness of the body-person to the world.¹⁴ The dialogical structure of the human person in relation to the world plays itself out through a process of active and creative engagement with the world. In this process, body-persons transcend the boundaries of one's embodied existence and reach out toward wider spheres of interaction. Moreover, the engagement with the world through activity ensures human solidarity with the past and future generations. Society as it exists is the incarnation of the labour of past generations of human community and our

participation in society is a manifestation of our solidarity with the past generations. Our present contribution to the betterment of society expresses our solidarity with the future generations insofar as they are the beneficiaries of our present labour. Thus, the openness to the world, the transcending of boundaries and the solidarity with humanity as a whole facilitated by human activity that follows from embodiment are integral dimensions of becoming an authentic human person. As we shall see, human activity also represents the process of the actualisation of human freedom.

Human Being as Dynamic:

So far we have specified a number of constitutive elements or dimensions of the human person. A careful look at these dimensions convinces us that they point toward the dynamic nature of the human person. They underline the fact that to be a human person means to be engaged in the *process* of becoming a human person. In other words, human existence itself is a constant becoming. From this point of view, a static understanding of human beings can only be an abstraction devoid of any foundation in reality. The human person is always in the process of becoming human and, therefore, the human person, as the various dimensions emphasize, is dynamic and this dynamism is the defining factor of the human person.

Human Beings as Free:

In theological anthropology this dynamism of the human person is expressed by the concept of freedom. Since human existence, as we have already stated, is a dynamic process of becoming, we are justified in qualifying human existence itself as freedom.¹⁵

From a theological point of view, freedom can never be a discrete human attribute or quality along with other attributes. For it refers to the whole human existence actualising itself in consonance with the various constitutive dimensions of the human person. Thus, for example, the actualisation of human existence along the line of the dimension of human beings standing before God defines freedom in this sphere as the ability to respond to the love of God and the opposite as unfreedom. Similarly, the actualisation of human existence along the line of the dimension of human beings as body-persons defines

freedom in this sphere as the willingness and ability to become a body-gift to others and the opposite as unfreedom. As we shall see shortly, the image of God is constituted by these freedoms and the mirror image is fashioned by the unfreedoms.

Human Beings as The Image of God:

The biblical metaphor that evokes the self-realization of human persons in the diverse spheres of human existence is the *Imago Dei*.¹⁶ The image of God is not something static like a portrait. It is dynamic and provides a dynamic view of the human person. This dynamism, as already indicated, is oriented toward the attainment of the full stature of the human person. It reveals the essential truth about human persons, namely, their incomplete and unfinished nature, as well as their fundamental vocation to become persons through the actualisation of their multiple relationality.

Human Beings as Oriented Toward a Destiny:

As a dynamic metaphor of human existence from a Christian point of view, the image of God signifies the progressive nature of the human unfolding in the direction of God, who is the source and destiny of persons. Thus the full realization of the image of God in human persons and the realization of the destiny of human persons are synonymous. From this perspective, the existential self-actualisation of human beings in the various spheres of their relationality is directly and intimately linked with the final destiny of human persons. This connection makes it clear that the economy of salvation is not consequent upon the Fall. It is integral to the purpose of creation. The creation of human beings in the image and likeness of God affirms this fundamental truth.

Human Beings as Image of God in Christ:

Accordingly, the Incarnation, as popular theology often wrongly conceives, is not necessitated by the Fall. It is the gracious design of God that human beings become the image of God in union with Jesus Christ, and not apart from him. The incarnation confirms God's design. In him we see the unfolding of the human person in the direction of God and with him we, as human beings, also unfold in the direction of God. As stated earlier, this unfolding encompasses all the dimensions of the human person. Thus, Jesus Christ as the image of the invisible

God (Col.1:15) reveals to us what it means to be the image of God through the progressive realization of one's vocation to be an authentic human person.

Functional Approach to Sin

We have discussed the various constitutive elements or dimensions of the human person from the Christian anthropological point of view and indicated that these are the elements involved in the process of becoming an authentic human person. These elements cumulatively paint the picture of an ideal person from the Christian faith perspective. The Christian metaphor that evokes this ideal picture of the human is the *Imago Dei*. The various dimensions of this picture provide the point of reference for the understanding of sin. It is only with reference to these elements that we can approach the function of the doctrine of sin. That is to say, when we look at sin from the standpoint of the *Imago Dei*, we realize that sin functions as a counter image or a mirror image that is in radical opposition to all the fundamental dimensions of the human person as represented by the *Imago Dei*. In the remaining part of the paper we shall substantiate this with reference to each of the constitutive dimensions of being an authentic human person.

Inauthentic Human Existence in Relation to God:

As we have seen, the central theological affirmation about the human person is that he/she stands before God. The notion of creature emphasizes this dimension and the notion of grace qualifies this divine-human relationship as God's self-giving love. If standing before God and responding to God's love constitute a fundamental dimension of being authentically human, then the contrary implies the absence of this dimension and what emerges is the picture of a person who turns away from God, one who refuses to acknowledge one's dependence on God and one who rejects God's offer of love. Here the function of the doctrine of sin is to reveal the meaning of inauthentic human existence in relation to the divine-human relationship.

Inauthentic Human Existence in Relation to Humans:

The biblical testimony affirms that an inauthentic existence in relation to God has its consequences upon the other constitutive

dimensions of being authentically human. We shall examine the result of the rupture of relationship with God on the human-human relationship as implied in the creation of humankind as male and female. This relationship is founded on the divine –human relationship and, based on this foundation, human beings strive to fashion authentic existence through communion of persons in society. In this context, human sexuality becomes a force that empowers persons to move out of themselves toward others in communication, communion and intimacy. The embodied nature of human persons enables them to translate this force into the concrete action of becoming body-gift to others. In this way, the social, sexual and embodied dimensions of human persons promote authentic existence at the level of human-human relationship.

But the destruction of the primary divine-human relationship adversely affects the human-human relationship built on it. Accordingly, the life-giving communion among persons comes to be replaced by life-negating domination, discrimination, oppression and exploitation, which mark the end of mutuality and solidarity among persons in society. Similarly, human sexuality metamorphoses into a power for self-centredness, aggression and for possessing others to satisfy one's own selfish needs. Likewise, body becomes an instrument for self-aggrandizement, control, manipulation and self-seeking. These are indications of the loss of authenticity in the sphere of human-human relationship. In this context, the doctrine of sin reveals the meaning and reality of inauthentic existence at the levels of personal and social relationships.

Inauthentic Human Existence in Relation to The World:

Another area that is adversely affected by the destruction of the divine-human relationship is the relationship between humans and the world. As we have seen, an authentic human existence presupposes a healthy interdependence of human beings and their environment. Acknowledging oneself to be an integral part of the cosmic process and one's role as the care-taker of the world, the human being works for the well being of creation. Through creative engagement with the world, human beings not only contribute their share to the advancement of

creation, but also actualise themselves in the process. Thus, openness to the world made real through human activity enables human beings to realize their authentic human existence.

Conversely, an inauthentic human existence manifests itself in the distortion of the human-world relationship. The ecological interdependence assumes the characteristics of ecological domination, exploitation and destruction. The human engagement that is meant to advance the well-being of creation turns out to be the cause of ecological disaster. Human activity that is supposed to express human solidarity with the past and future generations and to contribute to the building up of society degenerates into a means to exploit the fruit of other peoples' labour and to advance one's own self-interest at the expense of others, thereby paving the way for social misery in the form of hunger and poverty, disease and underdevelopment. These cosmic and social consequences of inauthentic human existence in relation to the world are highlighted by the doctrine of sin.

Inauthentic Human Existence as Unfreedom:

As we move on to the analysis of freedom, we recall that earlier we described human existence itself as freedom. It is because both, existence and freedom, have to do with becoming. When human existence unfolds in such a way that it leads to an authentic human existence through the actualization of multiple relationality, then it becomes a manifestation of authentic freedom. If human existence evolves in the opposite direction through the denial and destruction of relationships, then it becomes an exercise of unfreedom. That is to say, authentic human existence results from real freedom, and unfreedom leads to inauthentic human existence. It is the function of the doctrine of sin to reveal the spheres of unfreedom in human beings and it does so by highlighting the consequences of the destruction of relationships in different areas. Thus, sin reveals the operation of unfreedom in turning away from God, in the refusal of the love of God, in the negation of communion among human persons, in converting sexuality into self-centredness, in transforming body into an instrument of self gratification, and in changing human engagement with the world into an ecologically destructive activity.

Inauthentic Human Existence as Death:

Finally, sin reveals the ultimate consequence of the operation of unfreedom in the multiple spheres of human relationships, namely, the cessation of becoming authentically human, which is the same as being separated from the final destiny. If human existence is destined to unfold into the full stature of a person, that is, the attainment of the fullness of life, then the separation from the final destiny would mean ceasing to be human, that is, death. Thus, in relation to human destiny, the doctrine of sin performs the function of revealing the nature of a life that is oriented to death.

Two Images of The Human Person:

On the basis of our discussion we can now affirm that there are two images of the human person: one reveals the authentic human person and the other reveals the opposite. They are not discrete images as two separate photographs. Though we have dealt with them separately, they are intertwined in human experience and are linked together like an object and its mirror image. In the absence of the object, its mirror image ceases to exist. What gives reality to the mirror image is the presence of the object. We realize that what matters is not the mirror image but the object, and the mirror image has significance only insofar as it helps focusing on the object.

These two images are the human person as the image of God and the human person as the image of sin. The former is the real and the latter is the mirror image. The image of the human person as the image of God reflects the beauty, the desirability and the greatness of being an authentic human person as described in the section “Anthropological Foundations”. The mirror image, on the other hand, reflects the monstrosity of an inauthentic human existence as described in the section “Functional Approach to Sin”. In reality the human person is neither totally the image of God nor totally its mirror image – the image of sin. The two images remain as two possibilities of human freedom. They perform the same function in contrary ways. While the image of God invites, attracts and persuades us to become the reality it represents, namely, an authentic human person, the mirror image discourages, repels and dissuades us from becoming inauthentic human beings and turns our attention back to the image of God as the ideal to achieve. In

this way, the doctrine of sin empowers a person to consciously seek authentic human existence by conforming oneself to the image of God.

Adam as The Mirror Image of Christ:

In the light of all that has been said so far, we can have a fresh look at Rom. 5:12 ff., where St. Paul contrasts the figure of Christ and the figure of Adam. Though v.12 is used as the key text for the doctrine of the original sin, including the origin of sin and its universality, Paul's actual intention seems to go far beyond it. Is not Paul presenting Jesus Christ as the image of God and Adam as the image of sin? Is he not presenting Adam as the mirror image of Christ? If so, then Paul is portraying authentic human existence vis-à-vis inauthentic human existence with the help of the figures of Christ and Adam. He does not merely draw the portrait, but also emphasizes the possibility of changing unfreedom into freedom and thereby the possibility of moving from inauthentic to authentic existence made available through the self-gift of God in Jesus Christ. Thus, we may say that at the core of Paul's doctrine of sin in Rom. 5:12ff. is the question of authentic human existence.

Conclusion

Our aim has been to reclaim an authentic doctrine of sin for the Christian faith. This required of us to re-position the doctrine within the larger soteriological framework. Though we have not fully succeeded in explicitly situating the doctrine of sin in the total sphere of Christian faith, we have brought the doctrine of sin out of its theological isolation by locating human persons within the Christian horizon of understanding and by dealing with sin in relation to the human person. The functional approach helped us to link the doctrine of sin with anthropological foundations and to underscore its theological function in Christian faith. We have discovered that the doctrine of sin functions as a mirror image of the real person as envisaged by the Christian faith, and it creates in us the motivation to become that which the mirror image reflects. In this way, the functional approach gives us a clear insight into the positive function of the doctrine of sin in the Christian religion.

From this we may draw some valuable conclusions for theology and Christian living. The first conclusion is that the doctrine of sin is functional in the scriptures. It reveals how human beings stand in relation to the divine economy of salvation. It tells us in what sense we need salvation. By revealing our actual location in comparison to the divine call to be authentically human, the doctrine of sin motivates us to recommit ourselves to the realization of the fullness of life offered to us in Jesus Christ. Since the role of sin is functional in the scriptures and the scriptures do not assign any ontological status to sin, it is important that in its approach to sin theology follows the lead of the scriptures.

Second, the functional approach to sin reconfirms the fact that the focus of the Christian faith is on the human person called to the fullness of life in Jesus Christ and not on sin. This call is inscribed in the very creation of human beings. That is to say, the call to the fullness of life is not something added to the human vocation after the Fall, or necessitated by sin. This being the case, the doctrine of sin merely helps us to determine our existence in relation to this call to fullness. The functional approach to sin, thus, reveals the relative and provisional character of the doctrine of sin.

Third, it follows that in any discussion on sin, the legal and moral aspects of sin must give way to the experience of sin in relation to the vocation to live an authentic life in its fullness through multiple relationships. For, the former tends to reduce sin to definite actions and the intentions behind the actions, while the latter links sin to the very process of becoming human. The functional approach convincingly shows that the purpose of the doctrine of sin is not primarily to verify the moral status of an action, but to corroborate the correspondence between the action and the goal of becoming an authentic human person.

Fourth, the functional approach to sin sheds fresh light on the sacrament of reconciliation. If the mirror image reveals the disintegration of relationships with God, with humans and with the world, then the sacrament of reconciliation needs to change its focus from the enumeration of sins, absolution and penance to the sacramental grace that initiates the process of the restoration of broken relationships in us. In this way, the sacrament of reconciliation becomes more an

exercise of freedom in favour of human life unfolding in the direction of God than a magical washing away of sin. This exercise of freedom comes to be fleshed out in the restoration of broken relationships.

Finally, the functional approach to the doctrine of sin invites us not to be bogged down by the negative feelings of fear, guilt and shame that often accompany sin, but to discover the positive dimensions of the doctrine of sin, namely, the beauty, desirability and the greatness of becoming an authentic human person and, thereby, to be empowered to strive toward a deeper realization of the fullness of life.

Notes and References

- 1 The treatment of sin in the following works will give us a fair idea of a biblical method in the approach to sin. Herbert Lockyer, *All the Doctrines of the Bible* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1964; Reprint, Secunderabad: Om-Authentic Books, 2007); Eugene LaVerdiere, "The Need for Salvation: A New Testament Perspective", *Theological Studies* 21, no.3 (Fall 1982): 227-238; Piet Schoonenberg, *Man and Sin: A Theological View* (London: Sheed and Ward, 1965); Alphonse Spilly, "Sin And Alienation in the Old Testament: The Personalist Approach", *Theological Studies* 21, no.3 (Fall 1982): 211-225.
- 2 This statement is applicable only if the discussion of sin ends with the analysis of biblical narratives and terminologies. But usually, biblical theologians attempt to bring sin into the experiential level, as an analysis of the works cited in the above footnote will testify.
- 3 For example, see Raymond J. Stovich, "Psychology and Salvation: Reflection Upon the Human Condition", *Theological Studies* 21, no.3 (Fall 1982): 255-264.
- 4 Examples of the sociological contribution to the understanding of sin can be found in Gregory Baum, *Religion and Alienation: A Theological Reading of Sociology* (New York: Paulist Press, 1975); Kay Carmichel, *Sin and Forgiveness: New Responses in a Changing World* (Glasgow: Ashgate, 2003).
- 5 Karl Rahner and Paul Tillich provide convincing example of using philosophical insights for understanding the doctrine of sin. Cfr. Karl Rahner, *Foundations of Christian Faith: And Introduction to the Idea of Christianity* (New York: Crossroad, 1992) and Paul Tillich, *Systematic Theology Vol. II: Existence and the Christ* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1957).

- 6 Ted Peters uses insights from genetics and evolution to analyze the Christian notion of sin. Cfr. Ted Peters, "The Genesis and Genetics of Sin", in *Sin and Salvation: Task of Theology Today III*, ed. Duncan Reid & Mark Worthing (Hindmarsh, Australia: ATF Press, 2003), 89-112.
- 7 Burke adopts a functional approach and explores the function of the original sin in Christian faith. However, he explains the function in relation to the significance of Jesus Christ for human beings. His argument seems to imply that the original sin necessitated the redemption in Christ, which is theologically an untenable position. Cfr. Patrick Burke, "Man Without Christ: An Approach to Hereditary Sin", *Theological Studies* 29, no.4 (March 1968): 4-18. In the present article my aim is to understand the function of sin in relation to human persons and their vocation to become authentic human persons.
- 8 An extensive discussion on the role of the horizon of understanding in perceiving the historical development of the doctrine of sin is found in Anthony C. Thiselton, *The Hermeneutics of Doctrine* (Grand Rapids, Michigan: William B Eerdmans, 2007), 257-308
- 9 The analysis that follows is mostly based on my earlier article on human person. Cfr. Mathew Jayanth, "Theology and Science on Human Person: Constructing a Theological Anthropology in Dialogue with Science", *Malabar Theological Review* 2, no.1 (2007): 3-26.
- 10 For a discussion on *dharma* as grace, see Mathew Jayanth, "Theology and Science", *Malabar Theological Review*, 9-10.
- 11 This idea is powerfully expressed in the *Pastoral Constitution of the Church in the Modern World*. See *Gaudium et Spes*, no.19. I am grateful to Fr. Kurien Kunnumpuram, S.J. for calling my attention to this reference.
- 12 The *Pastoral Constitution* states: "God did not create man a solitary being. From the beginning "male and female he created them" (Gen 1:27). The partnership of man and woman constitutes the first form of communion between persons." Cfr. *Gaudium et Spes*, no.12.
- 13 A comprehensive treatment of the significance of body is available in Mathew Jayanth, "Body Spirituality: Incarnation as an Invitation to an Embodied Spirituality", *Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies* 7, no.2 (July 2004): 112-135.
- 14 For a philosophical analysis of the connection between embodiment and action in the world, see, Johnson J. Puthenpurackal, "The Phenomenon of Work: The Way of Human Existence as Worldly and Bodily", *Divyadaan* 17, no.2 (2006): 137-49

- 15 The concept of human existence as freedom is taken from Haight who, in turn, works with the Rahnerian concept of freedom. Cfr. Roger Haight, "Sin And Grace", in *Systematic Theology: Roman Catholic Perspective Vol. II*, ed. Francis Schussler Fiorenza & John P. Galvin (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1991), 77-141. His discussion on freedom is found on pages 80-85.
- 16 The major interpretations of the meaning of the image of God can be found in Noreen L. Herzfeld, *In Our Image: Artificial Intelligence and the Human Spirit* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1990). The significance of the image of God for understanding human person is discussed in Mathew Jayanth, "Theology and Science", *Malabar Theological Review*, 6-7.